

NUMERICAL MODELING OF SOIL-SHAFT INTERACTION VALIDATED USING THE INSTRUMENTED HAYWARD BRIDGE IN CALIFORNIA

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ABSTRACT

Finite element methods can be used to analyze the dynamic responses of soil-foundation-structural systems during earthquakes. Therefore, the validation of finite element models with actual seismic recordings is required to benefit from their use in foundation seismic design. In this paper, the acceleration records from the Hayward-I580/238 bridge in California will be studied. At the Hayward-I580/238 bridge, three-component accelerometer recordings from two geotechnical downhole arrays at the surface and depths down to 90 meters were used. Furthermore, from 2011 through 2022, 15 earthquakes were recorded at these downhole arrays ranging from Mw 3.4 to Mw 6. However, this paper focuses on the earthquake events within the range of Mw 3.4 to Mw 4.4. Therefore, this study is limited to earthquakes up to Mw 4.4. In the first part of this study, a free-field model of the Hayward-I580/238 bridge site is built using the OpenSees software. Then, in the second part, a drilled shaft of the Hayward-I580/238 bridge is modeled. A comparison of the dynamic responses generated by OpenSees with the recorded data from the geotechnical downhole arrays will be used to validate the free-field model, and the acceleration responses from the free-field model will be applied to the drilled shaft. Then, the behavior of the drilled shaft under the applied seismic forces in terms of different calculated parameters (e.g., displacements, reaction forces, etc.) will be investigated. As a result of this study, despite the absence of actual acceleration recordings, obtaining the responses of the soil layers in various depths is possible using a numerical modeling method. In conclusion, not only OpenSees provides a tool for monitoring drilled shaft behavior during seismic events, it provides a robust tool for future drilled-shafts seismic designs.

Keywords: deep foundation, OpenSees, soil-foundation interaction, drilled shaft, seismic design

INTRODUCTION

Seismic activity poses a significant risk to infrastructure, especially in regions prone to earthquakes. Understanding the complex interactions between soil, ground motion, and structural response is essential for the development of effective seismic-resistant designs (Reyes & Chopra 2012, Mohammadzadeh et al. 2023). In the past century, eight out of the ten costliest earthquakes worldwide occurred in California, leading to the destruction of structures, transportation networks, and facilities. The state faces an approximate yearly financial impact of \$3.7 billion due to earthquakes. A significant portion, over 70%, of the estimated losses can be attributed to three primary regions: the combined area of Los Angeles, Long Beach, and Santa Ana; the San Francisco-Oakland-Fremont region; and the Riverside-San Bernardino-Ontario zone (Faeli & Motamed 2023). For more than thirty years, researchers have been working to gain deeper insights into the structural behavior of bridges by applying collected data (Gomez et al. 2013; Arici et al. 2003), and various assessment methodologies have been applied to examine the seismic responses (Mosquera et al. 2012). Due to the significant impact of ground dynamics and supporting foundations on the seismic response of bridge structures, sensors are installed in selected shafts during the renovation or construction process to investigate soil-structure interaction effects (Wang et al. 2022). Consequently, the available seismic records can potentially enhance our understanding of the soil-structure interaction effects on the seismic behavior of bridge structures (Shamsabadi et al. 2016). The objective of this paper is to study the seismic behavior of a drilled shaft at the Hayward Bridge site using the OpenSees software. Through the study of free field records at the Hayward Bridge site in

California as a part of the BRACE2 project (Bridge Rapid Assessment Center for Extreme Events) and conducting numerical modeling, this research aims to investigate the response of the free field and drilled shaft under seismic loadings. The paper begins with a detailed site description and an overview of the instrumentation used to gather data at the research location. The subsequent sections present the results of our free-field modeling and soil-shaft interaction modeling, offering insights into the displacement and acceleration response of the site under simulated earthquake events. Through the comparison of actual field measurements with our model outcomes, the efficacy of our modeling approach is validated and areas for further refinement are discussed. Subsequently, the performance of the drilled shaft under the exerted seismic forces will be examined in terms of various calculated parameters, such as displacements, and reaction forces. Consequently, this research demonstrates that it is feasible to acquire responses from soil layers at varying depths using a numerical modeling approach, even in the absence of actual acceleration recordings.

SITE DESCRIPTION AND INSTRUMENTS

This paper primarily examines the Hayward - Hwy 580/238 Interchange, which features a 14-span cast-in-place pre-stressed concrete box girder bridge (Fig. 1). Data for the study was gathered through the instrumentation of two boreholes, referred to as the east and west geotechnical downhole arrays in Fig. 2. Table 1 provides an in-depth description of these boreholes. The foundation of the research site consists of stiff black clay and hard to very hard brown slightly silty clay layers, which sit atop a green to greyish green, highly weathered, sheared, and partially serpentinized gabbro, as well as greyish green, highly weathered, and sheared serpentine rock formations (Jurassic-Cretaceous period). At the borehole near the east downhole array, the stiff black clay layer covering the weathered sheared rock measures approximately 1 m (3 ft) in thickness (Table 2). In contrast, other boreholes along the bridge reveal clayey and silty alluvial deposits with a thickness of around 9 m (29.5 ft). Based on data from Caltrans in 1984, the groundwater level at the site is found within 3 to 8 m (10 to 26 ft) from the ground surface (Caltrans 1984).

Fig. 1. Hayward - Hwy 580/238 Interchange featuring a 14-span cast-in-place pre-stressed concrete box girder bridge (Caltrans 2021).

Fig. 2. Location of West and East geotechnical downhole arrays (modified from Google Earth).

Table 1. Characteristics of the downhole instrumentation at Hayward Bridge

Geotechnical Downhole Array	Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)	Downhole Array depth (m)	Distance to Hayward bridge (m)	No. of Recorded Events	Sensor depths below ground surface (m)
East	37.6896	122.0962	91	30	3	0,9,30,91
West	37.6887	122.1074	91	625	12	0,5,9,18,37,91

Table 2. The foundation of the research site

East Geotechnical Downhole Array		West Geotechnical Downhole Array	
Thickness (m)	Soil Description	Thickness (m)	Soil Description
1	Stiff black clay	6	Black to brown silty clay
24	Brown highly weathered sheared Gabbro	18	Olive green highly weathered sheared partially serpentinized Gabbro with calcite veinlets

RECORDED EARTHQUAKE MOTIONS

The study utilized downhole arrays that extended to a depth of 91 m (298.5 ft) below the ground surface (bgs), equipped with triaxial accelerometers at various depths as documented in Table 1, with orientations of 90 degrees, 360 degrees, and vertical. From 2011 to 2022, a total of 15 earthquakes with magnitudes ranging from Mw 3.4 to 6 were recorded. These records included three events captured at the east geotechnical downhole array and 12 events at the west geotechnical downhole array. The characteristics of earthquake excitations captured at the east geotechnical borehole are shown in Table 3. The acceleration measurements have been obtained as processed data from the Center for Engineering Strong Motion Data (CESMD).

Table 3. Characteristics of earthquake excitations captured at east geotechnical borehole (CESMD)

Downhole Array	No.	Earthquake Name	Earthquake date	Magnitude	PGA (g)	Epicentral distance (km)
	1	Berkeley	2018	4.4 MW	0.017	23.2
East	2	San Lorenzo	2021	3.9 MW	0.032	2.9
	3	San Ramon	2021	3.9 MW	0.024	15.8

METHODOLOGY

In the current study, the OpenSees software, a widely-used platform for structural seismic analysis and modeling, was employed. The geotechnical borehole on the eastern side was chosen for analysis due to its closer proximity to the Hayward-Highway 580/238 interchange, which serves as the central focus of this paper. As a result, the recorded responses from the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley and 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo earthquake events, captured by the monitoring devices installed at the eastern geotechnical borehole, were utilized in this research to validate the free-field modeling. Consequently, the scope of this research is confined to seismic events not exceeding an Mw of 4.4. Based on the outcomes, the time history responses derived from the free-field model during the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley earthquake events were used as excitations applied to the drilled shaft model. Additionally, according to the Caltrans ARS tool, the design ground motion corresponding to a 975-year return period is around 1g. However, the earthquake event that has been used in this model is well below the design ground motion.

Free-field modeling

In the initial stage of this study, a site-specific free-field model was developed based on data collected from the geotechnical borehole in the eastern region. This model consisted of a 30-meter-tall column, with 90 elements delineated and each element measuring 0.33 meters in size. The soil was modeled using four-node quad elements within the context of the plane strain formulation. The PressureIndependentMultiYield model was selected to characterize the constitutive behavior of the soil, incorporating a series of related soil properties. The strength parameters of the model have been derived from the shear velocity (V_s) of the soil layers. This model accounts for the elastoplastic behavior of soil, which inherently results in hysteretic damping. Fig. 3 illustrates the measured shear wave velocity in depth at the east geotechnical array. To define the Lysmer-Kuhlemeyer (1969) dashpot, a viscous uniaxial material was employed, and a zeroLength element was used to connect the two specified dashpot nodes. Following this, shear velocity data from the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley and 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo earthquake events were applied to introduce bidirectional excitations to the model. Consequently, the model's response in terms of displacement and acceleration could be analyzed along its entire length. The results generated by this model can be compared with the measurements obtained by the geotechnical borehole instruments. This comparison will enable the validation of the free-field model's accuracy and efficacy in predicting the free-field response to seismic activity, ultimately contributing to the development of more robust seismic design approaches.

Fig. 4 displays the displacement time history at the ground surface of the model for the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley and 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo events. As illustrated in Fig. 4, the results derived from the model closely align with the field data collected by the recorders. Consequently, the model's effectiveness in determining the field's displacement at various elevations during an earthquake event can be confirmed. Fig. 5 presents a comparison between the acceleration time history at the ground surface, as derived from

the model, and the recorded data. Fig. 5 demonstrates the model's suitability for determining acceleration time history at different depths. Fig. 6 compares the spectral responses from the free-field model and field recorders for the mentioned events. The spectral velocity and spectral displacement results from the model are comparable to the data from the recorders. However, the spectral acceleration responses obtained from the model are lower than those recorded by the recorders. This discrepancy may be attributed to the damping value employed in the model. In the free-field model, damping is calculated based on predefined soil properties. The shear wave velocity for the soil is determined using the data provided by the eastern geotechnical borehole. However, data is lacking for the 10 to 20 m (33 to 65.6 ft) depth range. As a result, the V_s value for that depth has been reasonably estimated. This implies that the soil properties assigned to the model may deviate from the actual soil properties in the field.

Fig. 3. The V_s profile in the depth provided for the east geotechnical array (CESMD).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Displacement time history at the ground surface in the x-direction (channel 360°), (a) 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (b) 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo event.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5. Acceleration time history at the ground surface in the x-direction (channel 360°), (a) 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (b) 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo event.

Fig. 6. Spectral responses in the x-direction, (a) spectral acceleration, spectral velocity, and spectral displacement for 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (b) spectral acceleration, spectral velocity, spectral displacement, and for 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo event.

Soil-shaft interaction modeling

In the following part of the paper, a model of the drilled shaft is created, and the acceleration responses obtained from the free-field model during the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley earthquake event are integrated. The shaft nodes are created with three dimensions and six degrees of freedom. This model comprised a 12-meter-tall column, with 36 elements defined and a size of 0.33 meters for each element. The shaft exhibits elastic behavior through the use of an elastic section object in collaboration with the displacement-based beam element (`dispBeamColumn`). The interaction between the soil and the shaft is considered by an array of springs in two distinct directions, while zero-length elements are employed for connecting the defined spring nodes. The constitutive behavior of these springs is characterized in such a way that springs in the lateral directions (x and y directions) serve as p-y springs. As the p-y curves defined in the OpenSees software predominantly relate to sandy soil, a hysteretic constitutive model is employed to represent the p-y curve for clay and weak rock, which make up the soil layers at the site. The essential parameters for the hysteretic model in clay and weak rock are derived from the acquired p-y curves, following the method by Rees et al. Fig.7 shows the obtained p-y curves for weak rock and stiff clay. Displacement time histories from the free-field model are used as excitations for the model in two directions, and the results are gathered. Fig. 8 illustrates the displacement time history of the shaft at the

ground surface in both directions. As demonstrated in Fig. 8, the peak deflection of the drilled shaft head occurs at approximately $t = 32$ s. The maximum values obtained in the x and y directions are similar, with both being around 3×10^{-4} m (0.001 ft). Fig. 9 illustrates the relative displacement of the drilled shaft from the tip at different depths and time intervals. As evident from Fig. 9, the highest displacement in both directions consistently transpires at the ground surface for all considered time points. As anticipated, the relative displacement values in the x-direction exhibit slight differences compared to the results obtained in the y-direction, owing to the distinct excitations applied in each direction. Fig. 10 displays the soil reaction at different depths for specific time instances in both x and y directions. As illustrated in Fig. 10, the peak soil reaction occurs at a depth of approximately 3.5 m (11.5 ft) from the ground surface during predetermined periods in both directions. Based on the outcomes from the soil-shaft interaction model, at $t = 30$ s, the highest soil reaction value in the x-direction is about 30 kN/m, while the corresponding value in the y-direction is approximately 52 kN/m.

Fig. 7. Obtained p-y curves (a) for weak rock in different depths, (b) for stiff clay at 1m depth.

Fig. 8. Displacement time history of shaft head obtained from OpenSees analysis for 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (a) x-direction (channel 360°), (b) y-direction (channel 90°).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9. Relative displacement of the shaft from tip in-depth obtained from OpenSees analysis for 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (a) x-direction (channel 360°), (b) y-direction (channel 90°).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 10. Soil reaction in the depth of drilled shaft obtained from OpenSees analysis for 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley event, (a) x-direction (channel 360°), (b) y-direction (channel 90°).

DISCUSSION

In the process of modeling free-field conditions, a slight difference has been observed between accelerations derived from the model and those measured by recorders. It should be noted that the model's damping predominantly originates from the inherent damping outlined in the soil's constitutive model, which is linked to input parameters. Due to insufficient data on soil shear velocity at specific depths, the input parameters may not accurately represent actual field conditions. For the 2018 Mw 4.4 Berkeley earthquake event (PGA = 0.017), there is only a slight difference between model outcomes and recorded measurements. However, a more significant discrepancy is evident for the 2021 Mw 3.9 San Lorenzo event (PGA = 0.032). These findings suggest that the spectral accelerations generated by the model may not align precisely with field results, particularly for high PGA events. However, the time (period) at which the maximum spectral acceleration occurs is comparable to the results of recorders and the model. Additionally, displacement time histories are the most critical output from the free-field model, as they serve as excitations for the soil-shaft interaction model. It is worth noting that the model's displacement time histories correspond well with recorded data. In terms of soil-shaft interaction modeling, an elastic section is incorporated for the shaft. At the given level of applied motion, it is anticipated that the model will display an elastic response. However, larger magnitude earthquakes could provoke a distinctly different reaction within the model. Therefore, to achieve more precise results at heightened motion levels, the use of an inelastic section may be more suitable. Additionally, in the field, excitations are also applied to the shaft in the z-direction. This necessitates the incorporation of a series of springs in the z-direction to improve the model.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study presents an analysis of the seismic responses of the drilled shaft, focusing on the Hayward - Hwy 580/238 Interchange. Utilizing data from two geotechnical boreholes and the OpenSees software, the research employed site data for analyzing the drilled shaft response to seismic events. The development of a free-field model and its subsequent validation demonstrated its effectiveness in obtaining the responses of drilled shafts to seismic activity. The study also incorporated soil-shaft interaction modeling by creating a drilled shaft model, which integrated time history responses from the free-field model. Excitations are applied over the length of the modeled drilled shaft as displacement time histories in two directions, and the behavior of the shaft is investigated. Overall, this research contributes valuable insights into the seismic response of the Hayward - Hwy 580/238 Interchange, advancing our understanding of ground motion responses and the bridge structure's reaction to seismic events. This study demonstrates that, even in the absence of actual acceleration recordings, it is possible to obtain the responses of soil layers at various depths using a numerical modeling method. In conclusion, OpenSees not only offers a means for monitoring drilled shaft behavior during seismic events but also provides a robust predictive model for future seismic designs of drilled shafts. The findings underscore the importance of accurate modeling and validation for improving seismic design approaches and enhancing the resilience of infrastructure. Future work should aim to address the limitations in the current model, such as refining damping values and soil properties, as well as extending the analysis to incorporate other seismic events and additional infrastructure components.

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